

Origin myths among the tribes and lower castes of Kerala - A Comparative Analysis

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Introduction

Myths are part of social life and they play an important role in social organisation. They reflect fundamental beliefs, rights and values of a group and give an idea of the social heritage of the particular folk. The term *myth* also refers to the imaginative expression in narrative form of what is experienced or apprehended as basic reality. They are carried from generation to generation traditionally and often considered as a major category in oral folklore. As per Maria Leach and Jerome Fried, 'a myth is a story, presented as having actually occurred in a previous age, explaining the cosmological and supernatural traditions of a people, their gods, heroes, cultural traits, religious beliefs, etc. The purpose of myth is to explain, and, as Sir G.L. Gomme said, myths explain matters in "the science of a pre-scientific age." Thus myths tell of the creation of man, of animals, of landmarks; they tell why a certain animal has its characteristics (e.g. why the bat is blind or flies only at night), why or how certain natural phenomena came to be (e.g. why the rainbow appears or how the constellation Orion got into the sky), how and why rituals and ceremonies began and why they continue.'

Myth is always an account of a creation or a formation and it explains how something was produced; began to be. Myths tell the stories of ancestors and the origin of humans, the world, the gods, demigods and supernatural beings. They are generally classified into higher myths and Lower myths. Myths related to the origin of something; a deity, natural phenomena, plants, animals, man or a race comes under the category of origin myths. Both higher and lower myths include plenty of origin myths.

In this paper, I am trying to analyze some of the origin myths that exist in the lower castes of Kerala. These stories as we shall see are a great resource for understanding the structure and functions of lower myths. They can also used as an important tool in the study of the formation of the caste system in Kerala.

Some Mythical Narratives :

Let us examine some of the narratives existing among the lower order of the caste-hierarchy in Kerala Regarding the origin of their caste.

1. Thiyya:
 - a) According to Thiyya origin mythology Lord Shiva created them to gather toddy from the palm tree.
 - b) Originated from the right thigh of Shiva.

2. Kuravar :
 - a) Kuravar believes that they were born (Kakkalan) from the sacred fire made for destroying the evil eye that affected Shiva.
 - b) Another story about Kuravas says that they were created by Parvathi- Parameswara.
 - c) They were born as the sons of Lord Subrahmania and Valli, the adopted daughter of Nakli, a tribal chief.

3. Thiyyadi: They believe that they were Brahmins at first but later degraded in the caste-hierarchical order by the curse of Parvathi-Parameswara.

4. Paraya: Parayas also share the same faith in relation with their origin.

5. Vannan: Vannan has his own story about his origin. Regarding the origin of their caste, they believe that they were the ones who put make-up on Parameswara during the Tandava dance. They also believe that their women were the ones who washed Parvati's clothes.

6. Kusavar Sage: Kulala was the fore-father of Kusava Caste- so says their oral narratives.

7. Mannan/ Velan:
 - a. Once Parvati made an elephant(ana) out of clay(mannu) and Lord Shiva accidentally snatched it. Soon a man emerged from it. They called him Mannan, meaning he who came from the dust. Velans also believes that Subramanian gave them the Vel.
 - b. On one occasion Shiva appeared in disguise as a Velan to evoke Vishnu from his drowsiness and thus the caste Velan was created.

8. Washer men Perumamannan(Lower Cast) &Veluthedan (Middle layer Caste -) Both of them share the same origin myth with some differences. They both believe that they originated from a lump in the thigh of Lord Shiva.

9. Pulluvan: as per the 'Karma Sasthram Pattu', a popular folk song among Pulluvas they believe that their origin is from the marital relationship of Manda pala and Jaritha.
 - b. Another story about Pulluvan's origin is that they were created by the Brahma-Vishnu-Maheswara, from sacred grass (darbha). The deities gave them the duty to play Veena (Lyre) and kutam (a pot used as a musical instrument) to please snakes.
 - c. A fellow named, Mahadevan performed 'Naveru Pattu' after birth of Sree Ganapati. (Naveru pattu-a ritualistic song performed by pulluvas to eradicate all the evils out of the body). A person named Puliveli Nayar had a forbidden relation with a Brahmin woman. So he was expelled from his caste. Mahadeva met him and gave his lyre to Puliveli Nayar. He also gave the right to perform Naveru Pattu as a means of living .
10. Panan: Folk songs of Panas/Malayans describe the story of their fore-father-Thiruvarangathu pananar who was a fellow of Lord Shiva. He once eradicated the evil-eye that affected Shiva.

Let us now examine some of the beliefs related to their origin that exist in tribal communities of Kerala.

11. Kanikkar: Lord Subrahmanya married a Kurava named Valli. These tribe believe that they are the sons of these couple.
12. Mannan : According to Mannans they were the beloved servants of King Pandya of Madhura.
13. Paniyan: Once there were a woman and man. They had a very strange relationship. Regarding the upper part of the body they were said to be sister and brother. But below the waist they were husband and wife. Paniyans were born out of their relationship.
14. Nattumalayan: (Sub division of Malaya Community)
 - a. They considered themselves to be the descendants of Shiva and Parvathi.
 - b. Some believe that the women are the descendants of Surpanakha.
 - c. In ancient times they were Nairs and were brought to a state of degradation by the reprehensible conduct of their women who were out casted owing to their illicit intercourse with low caste men.

3. Analysis

Melville J. Herskovits gives us a clue for the hidden meaning of the myth No. 2.2.3 (of Paniyas). He writes: "In this indeed we find a psycho analytic mechanism at work wherein customary behaviour is often distorted in a manner that tells as much about the desires individuals must suppress in order to conform. It is enough in this connection to mention how, in Indonesian and Malasian groups where rigid brother sister sexual taboos obtain. The origin myths often tell of the beginning of mankind in the incestuous relation of a brother and sister. (1974-p-271)

The ethno centrism of the folk is best illustrated in their origin myths. Ethnocentrism denotes a positive orientation toward those sharing the same ethnicity and a negative one toward others.

All these origin myths are local narratives and many of them are folk versions of the higher mythology that found in elite tradition and its epic literature. Generally speaking, these stories belong to the category of Lower Mythology. Most of them are prevalent within a particular community and It is a narrative that applies only to them. The persons outside the folk may not be aware of these folk narratives. These myths reflect the esoteric concepts of itself. They are also endemic in nature.

These stories are not much ancient in nature. We know that the caste like Panan and Velan are vividly described in Sangham literature. But we cannot find out any evidence of these narratives in those ancient literature. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that these myths are created by the folks in connection with the establishment of the caste system which happened only after 10th century and by the process of Aryanisation. Though the historical element in local narrative may be minimum these myths can be used as an important tool in the study of Kerala historiography.

We can see a duality in structure and function in the case of the origin myths of the lower castes. All these folks identify themselves with their occupation in the caste system implemented by the higher caste. But in the mean time they also reject the concept established by the ruling caste that the people in the lower order are cursed people. By creating their own origin myth the lower caste substitute the view that they are also the beloved sons of the God and directly created from His power. Here these myths are used as a tool for resistance and adjustment in the process of adaptation of the caste system.

But the prevailing beliefs among the adivasis have little to do with the dominant culture. The origin myths among tribes have a very distant relation with the higher mythology and elite tradition. They are more independent and unique in nature. This becomes more significant when we consider the fact that the process of Aryanization has not been significantly extended to the tribes and they are generally excluded from the caste system of Kerala. Narratives of the nature of aggregation, exclusion, degradation or power struggle, as seen in the lower castes, are not commonly found among the tribals.

All these origin myths justify the traditional occupations (kulathozhil) of the particular society. According to them God himself gave them the right to do their conventional means of living and there is an element of divinity in their job. By the transmission of these myths they also insist the next generation to pursue the traditional livelihood. Thus these myths help to build up a strong sense of group solidarity. As

Malinowsky observed 'it serves as a warrant, a character and often even particular guide to their social structure and mode of living.'

The myths existing in the lower castes of Kerala are directly connected to Lord Shiva. Considering the argument that Shiva is an Aryanised Dravidian deity this aspect will shed more light on the ancient history of these lower castes and Dravidian society in general. It is also interesting to note that there is no such importance to Shiva in the tribal's myths. This is another distinguished character of origin myths of the tribes.

Like all other folklore, these origin myths also played important functions in the social life of these folks. Many of these stories change over time as society evolves. For example 'Panan Varavu Pattu', performed by Panans now a days during the marriage ceremony in some Christian families of Central Travancore describes "Thiruvarangathu Pan
anars' as a companion of St. Thomas who established Christianity in Kerala. According to these song St. Thomas himself gave them the right to perform 'Panan Varavu Pattu. It is through these transformations of the myth that the society is able to adapt to social changes. Here the myth maintains the folk's social adjustment in accordance with the changing social circumstance.

Let us analyse the myth exist in Thiyya, Paraya, Mannan, Nattumalayan etc. These myths relate how one state of affair become another in common. The caste Kuruppu had also a similar origin-myth. They believed that they were upgraded from sudra-lower caste. The paper generated from the discussion at the workshop in myth and folk tale held during Indo-American Seminar on Indian Folklore at CIIL, Mysore explored similar exchanges or movements of characters between lower middle and higher castes. The participants found that the basic structure of transformation in Indian folktales resembles the outline for Hindu social organisation generally. They also argued that the following three might be particularly important key to the study of Indian examples.

High / Low

Power / Purity

Inside / Outside

After analyzing the origin myths of Kerala we can redraw the structure as follows.

Reference:

Melville. J. Herskovits, Cultural Anthropology, 1974.

2. Bromislaw Malinowski, Magic, Science & Religion, 1992.